

Carimbo de data/hora	Consent to participate in t	1. Are you a father (biolog	2. In what country do you	In what state do you live?	How old are you?
06/04/2023 16:46:49	Agree	Yes	Brazil	BA	37 to 42 years
06/04/2023 21:30:51	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Piauí	31 to 36 years
06/04/2023 22:08:55	Agree	Yes	Brazil	São Paulo	37 to 42 years
07/04/2023 00:17:12	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	31 to 36 years
07/04/2023 09:11:20	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	43 to 47 years
07/04/2023 09:11:32	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	31 to 36 years
07/04/2023 09:40:31	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceara	31 to 36 years
07/04/2023 10:24:00	Agree	Yes	Brazil	CEARA	43 to 47 years
07/04/2023 10:28:43	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	37 to 42 years
07/04/2023 10:46:57	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	31 to 36 years
07/04/2023 11:11:01	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	43 to 47 years
07/04/2023 12:07:03	Agree	Yes	Brazil	São Paulo	37 to 42 years
07/04/2023 13:37:56	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	37 to 42 years
07/04/2023 17:48:40	Agree	Yes	United Kingdom	Oxfordshire	43 to 47 years
08/04/2023 08:00:39	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	more than 61 years
08/04/2023 09:15:01	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Paraná	43 to 47 years
08/04/2023 22:03:25	Agree	Yes	United States	Florida	43 to 47 years
09/04/2023 15:01:43	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	26 to 30 years
09/04/2023 21:49:33	Agree	Yes	Germany	LZ	37 to 42 years
10/04/2023 02:54:03	Agree	Yes	Brazil	PE	43 to 47 years
10/04/2023 06:50:27	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Luxembourg	31 to 36 years
10/04/2023 07:54:25	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceará	31 to 36 years
10/04/2023 08:30:18	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceará	26 to 30 years
10/04/2023 09:12:01	Agree	No			
10/04/2023 09:29:19	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceará	26 to 30 years
10/04/2023 09:32:01	Agree	Yes	Brazil	CE	26 to 30 years

What is your marital status	What is the highest level of education	How many children do you have	How old is your youngest child	Do your child (or children) have a disability	What is your family income
Married	PhD	1	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	Less than 1 year	Yes	Up to 9 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	1	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	Graduated	1	Less than 1 year	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	Up to 3 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	4	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Graduated	2	Less than 1 year	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 3 minimum wages
Long-term relationship	PhD	1	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	2	More than 12 years	No	Up to 7 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Less than 1 year	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Graduated	1	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	3	Less than 1 year	No	Up to 3 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	2	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Undergraduate Student	2	More than 12 years	Yes	Up to 9 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	Graduated	1	Less than 1 year	Yes	Up to 3 minimum wages
Long-term relationship	Especialization	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 3 minimum wages

Are you currently employed?	What is the nature of your work?	Do you work in the software industry?	How many years of experience do you have?	How many employees do you manage?	How many members are on your team?
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	State Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Industry	Between 7 and 9 years	More than 600 employees	From 16 to 20
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	Between 7 and 9 years	From 21 to 49 employees	From 16 to 20
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry	Between 1 and 3 years	From 100 to 199 employees	From 11 to 15
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	Between 1 and 3 years	Up to 20 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work face to face	Research/collaboration project	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	Between 7 and 9 years	More than 600 employees	From 16 to 20
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	Between 4 and 6 years	More than 600 employees	More than 21
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	Between 10 and 12 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	Between 7 and 9 years	From 400 to 599 employees	From 6 to 10

How many years of exper	How many members are	How many years of exper	Regarding your industry	Regarding your industry	Regarding your academic
Between 7 and 9 years	From 21 to 49 members				
Between 4 and 6 years	Up to 20 members				
		Between 10 and 12 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10	Between 7 and 9 years
More than 15 years	More than 600 members				
More than 15 years	From 50 to 99 members				
Between 10 and 12 years	From 21 to 49 members				
Between 4 and 6 years	From 50 to 99 members				
Between 1 and 3 years	From 21 to 49 members				
More than 15 years	From 200 to 399 members				
		More than 15 years	Up to 20 employees	From 16 to 20	More than 15 years
		Between 7 and 9 years	From 50 to 99 employees	From 11 to 15	Between 4 and 6 years
Between 13 and 15 years	From 50 to 99 members				
		More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10	Between 13 and 15 years

Regarding your academic	What is the main role you	How many women are the	How many women have k	How long was your patern	Would you like your pater
	Professor and Researcher	From 7 to 10	3	15	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor	Less than 3	None	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Data Scientist	Less than 3	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
More than 600 members	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3	None	from 51 to 60 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	From 11 to 15	More than 5	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	DevOps	Less than 3	2	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Cto	From 4 to 6	1	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	From 7 to 10	2	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Researcher	From 7 to 10	More than 5	from 31 to 40 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	Less than 3	None	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Project Manager	From 16 to 20	4	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Data Scientist	Less than 3	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	From 7 to 10	1	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Researcher	Less than 3	1	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	More than 21	2	I did not take paternity leave	Yes, I'd like more days.
From 400 to 599 members	Human-Computer Interaction	Less than 3	2	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	Less than 3	None	more than 120 days	No, it was enough.
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3	None	I did not take paternity leave	No, it was enough.
From 21 to 49 members	Professor and Researcher	Less than 3	1	I did not take paternity leave	No, it was enough.
	Professor and Researcher	From 11 to 15	2	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
Up to 20 members	Software Engineer	From 7 to 10	2	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3	2	I did not take paternity leave	No, it was enough.
	Designer	From 7 to 10	1	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	From 4 to 6	1	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Product Owner	Less than 3	More than 5	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.

Did you return to the same position and company after becoming father?	If you have changed your	How many employments	Did you maintain the sam
Yes, same role and company		None	Yes
Yes, same role and company	Not applicable.		1 Yes
Yes, same role and company			1 Yes
Yes, same role and company			1 Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company			1 No
Yes, same role and company			1 Yes
Yes, same role and company		None	Yes
Yes, same role and company			1 Yes
Yes, same role and company			1 Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	No
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company			1 Yes
Yes, same role and company		None	Yes
No, same role and another company			1 Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
No, another role and another company	I wasn't working when I ha	None	No
Yes, same role and company			2 Yes
Yes, same role and company			1 Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	No
Yes, same role and company			1 Yes
Yes, same role and company			2 No
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
No, another role and another company	Melhoria salarial para um		2 Yes

Did you work during your	If you worked during your	After you returned to work	Who performs more child	Would you like to participa	If you do not contribute ec
Partially	As a researcher, my duties kept the same (reviewing		The mother does more.	Yes	I wish I could have more t
Yes	I was the computer science course coordinator at th		The mother does more.	Yes	Work activities. The moth
No			The mother does more.	Yes	After finishing my paternit
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	I do contribute equally
Partially	Deadlines.		The mother does more.	Yes	Child focuses more on the
No			We do share child caregiv	No	-
Partially	Just need to have a few customers meetings that ne		The mother does more.	Yes	The work take more of my
Partially	orientação de aluno (só os mais importantes para m		The mother does more.	Yes	na maioria das vezes são
No			I tend to do more childcar	Yes	
No			The mother does more.	Yes	The child is more attached
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	I do contribute equally
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	We do share equally
No			The mother does more.	Yes	I can not give milk
No			The mother does more.	Yes	My partner has stopped w
Yes			We do share child caregiv	Yes	Fata e tempo
Yes	A legislação brasileira, e o tempo para cumprir o dc		We do share child caregiv	Yes	No. Eu contribui o máximo
No			We do share child caregiv	No	Na
No	I wasn't employed. But I was still studying to gradua		We do share child caregiv	Yes	I am working and my part
Yes			The mother does more.	Yes	oveseas for my work awa
					Optamos por não ter babá
Partially	Responder email, basicamente		The mother does more.	Yes	Durante a fase de distanc
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	.
No			I tend to do more childcar	Yes	N/D
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	.
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	I contribute equally to par
Partially	Entrega de projetos		The mother does more.	No	Eu trabalho e ela fica mai

After becoming father, have you ever faced any	Have you ever faced any	In your opinion, do you think	In your opinion, do you think	What challenges and difficulties	In your opinion, what challenges
Overload (related to child)	Work-like balance is high	Definitely	Possibly	lack of enough time (neither)	I can't answer.
Sleep deprivation (related to child)	No.	Possibly	Definitely	I struggle to meet all demands	I have no idea. I would guess
Sleep deprivation (related to child)	No, I haven't.	Possibly	Possibly	At the time, due to the crisis	Mothers, because they are
Overload (related to child)	No	Definitely	Definitely	Tem dias que é bastante	Acredito que mães tender
Overload (related to child)	No	Definitely	Definitely	Time restraints.	Double workload, time res
Lack of confidence, Overload	No	Definitely Not	Definitely Not	None	None
Overload (related to child)	No.	Possibly	Definitely Not	Is more difficult to concentrate	Same as the parent but in
Overload (related to child)	de maneira geral não. apenas	Definitely	Definitely	sinceramente não sei dizer	a lista é imensa: preconce
Lack of confidence, Overload		Definitely Not	Definitely Not	Adaptar horários e tentar	Sobrecarga de atividades
Overload (related to child)	No	Probably Not	Probably Not	I have less time to work	physical and emotional ex
Lack of confidence, Overload	No	Possibly	Possibly	Quando o pai é muito pre	Normalmente obrigam, sil
High physical and mental	No	Possibly	Possibly	As a father we need to sh	I think it's harder for mom
Overload (related to child)	Only to be always tired	Possibly	Possibly	Less time to do the work	Less time to do the work a
Lack of confidence, Overload	I don't think so	Probably	Probably Not	Not enough childcare hou	Diseases often mean the
Overload (related to child)	Nao	Possibly	Probably Not	Lidar com meus estudantes	ser profissional e mãe ao
Overload (related to child)	Diminui muito o rendimento	Definitely	Definitely	Preconceito pois muito se	As metas são difíceis para
Lack of confidence, Overload	No	Probably	Possibly	Less availability and more	Don't know
None	Of course. I have to drive	Definitely	Definitely	I have to take him to scho	Overload of work. Distrust
it made me more driven and	no	Possibly	Probably Not	none, except to keep going	no idea
Overload (related to child)	Não que eu tenha perceb	Probably	Possibly	Conciliar reuniões e horár	Carga mental com preocu
Overload (related to child)	No.	Probably	Probably	More responsibility to ma	More responsibility to ma
Overload (related to child)	No	Definitely	Probably	N/D	N/D
Overload (related to child)	Sim. Sinto que as pessoas	Definitely	Probably	Gestão de tempo; perda c	Gestão de tempo; diminui
Overload (related to child)	No.	Probably	Probably	Collabore equality in pare	Probaly in some works mo
Lack of confidence, Overload	Sim. Perca de foco	Possibly	Probably	Como eu trabalho em casa	Além da expectativa salar

At work, do you believe th	What are your suggestion	Are you willing to implement friendly actions for moms and dads at work?		
I have no idea.	Adapting the workplace to	Possibly		
Maybe yes. It depends on	Perhaps, reduced working	Definitely		
I think yes.	Extend the paternity leave			
Usually the concern is gre	Allow alternative work sch	Definitely		
Sim. Fatores como a ama	As empresas deveriam ec	Definitely		
Yes. As per described diff	1 year leave for caring for	Definitely		
Dependendo da empresa	Todo filho exige atenção,	Definitely		
I guess so, usually fathers	Companies should be flex	Definitely		
não saberia dizer com de	flexibilidade de horários, e	Possibly		
Não		Definitely		
Yes. Mothers have more c	Having a support network	Possibly		
No Governo não, existe u	A pandemia melhorou mu	Probably		
I think so as we have see	Probably we need to disc	Definitely		
Mother's have difficulty to	Give long licenses for bot	Definitely		
Yes.	More and better childcare	Probably		
Hoje um dia não acho iss	Dividir sempre a carga de	Definitely		
Pra mulher é muito mais c	Não temos suporte das 2	Probably		
Yes, probably. For smalle	Longer leave, flexible ram	Probably		
Yes. Not only they tend to	End capitalism.	Definitely		
.	.	Definitely		
Sim. Crianças tendem a t	Flexibilidade de horários,	Definitely		
Probably most part of the	Divide responsibilities.	Definitely		
N/D	N/D	Definitely		
Sim. A sobrecarga matern	Grupos de apoio; flexibilic	Definitely		
Yes, because in many cas	Create a sleep routine to	Definitely		
Acredito que sim, devido	Não sei..	Probably Not		

Carimbo de data/hora	Consent to participate in t	1. Are you a father (biolog	2. In what country do you	In what state do you live?	How old are you?
10/04/2023 09:57:51	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	26 to 30 years
10/04/2023 09:59:15	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceará	31 to 36 years
10/04/2023 10:25:15	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceará	37 to 42 years
10/04/2023 10:47:15	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	26 to 30 years
10/04/2023 12:07:41	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceará	21 to 25 years
10/04/2023 12:31:01	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	48 to 54 anos
10/04/2023 12:31:51	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Rio Grande do Norte	31 to 36 years
10/04/2023 13:27:35	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	43 to 47 years
10/04/2023 13:42:47	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceará	31 to 36 years
10/04/2023 14:00:13	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceará	37 to 42 years
10/04/2023 14:12:58	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	more than 61 years
10/04/2023 14:45:52	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	43 to 47 years
10/04/2023 14:46:54	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	43 to 47 years
10/04/2023 15:34:33	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	43 to 47 years
10/04/2023 16:40:54	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Brasilia	43 to 47 years
10/04/2023 16:56:31	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Goias	31 to 36 years
10/04/2023 18:23:17	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	31 to 36 years
10/04/2023 18:33:54	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Tocantins	26 to 30 years
10/04/2023 20:47:43	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	31 to 36 years
10/04/2023 21:12:41	Agree	Yes	Brazil	São Paulo	37 to 42 years
11/04/2023 00:00:20	Agree	Yes	Brazil	BA	43 to 47 years
11/04/2023 09:14:54	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	31 to 36 years
11/04/2023 11:01:55	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	43 to 47 years
11/04/2023 11:11:10	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	43 to 47 years
11/04/2023 11:33:02	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	48 to 54 anos
11/04/2023 11:59:46	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	37 to 42 years

What is your marital status	What is the highest level of education	How many children do you have	How old is your youngest child	Do your child (or children) have a disability	What is your family income
Long-term relationship	Graduated	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Divorced	Especialization	1	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	Up to 3 minimum wages
Married	Master	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Single	Graduated	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 3 minimum wages
Married	Graduated	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	Master	3	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 7 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	1	Between 4 and 6 years	No	Up to 7 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	3	Less than 1 year	Yes	Up to 9 minimum wages
Married	Master	4	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	4	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Graduated	1	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 9 minimum wages
Married	Graduated	2	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 9 minimum wages
Married	Master	2	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	More than 12 years	No	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	1	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	Master	2	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Divorced	PhD	2	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages

Are you currently employed?	What is the nature of your work?	Do you work in the software industry?	How many years of experience do you have?	How many employees does your organization have?	How many members are there in your organization?
Yes, and I work remotely/	Private software development	Industry	Between 1 and 3 years	From 50 to 99 employees	From 11 to 15
Yes, and I work remotely/	Research/collaboration project	Industry	Between 7 and 9 years	From 400 to 599 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Private software development	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 11 to 15
Yes, and I work remotely/	Private software development	Industry	Between 1 and 3 years	From 50 to 99 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely/	Private software development	Industry	Between 4 and 6 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	From 200 to 399 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely/	Private software development	Industry	Between 13 and 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work face to face	Open source software project	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely/	Private software development	Industry	Between 13 and 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 16 to 20
Yes, and I work face to face	Open source software project	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	More than 21
Yes, and I work remotely/	Federal Public Administration	Industry	Between 13 and 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 11 to 15
Yes, and I work remotely/	Private software development	Industry	More than 15 years	From 400 to 599 employees	From 16 to 20
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely/	Private software development	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Industry	Between 10 and 12 years	From 50 to 99 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely/	Private software development	Industry	Between 4 and 6 years	Up to 20 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely/	Federal Public Administration	Industry	Between 10 and 12 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 11 to 15
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely/	State-owned company (Software)	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely/	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			

How many years of exper	How many members are	How many years of exper	Regarding your industry	Regarding your industry	Regarding your academic
Between 13 and 15 years	From 50 to 99 members				
Between 10 and 12 years	From 21 to 49 members				
More than 15 years	From 21 to 49 members				
Between 13 and 15 years	More than 600 members				
		Between 13 and 15 years	Up to 20 employees	From 6 to 10	Between 10 and 12 years
Between 4 and 6 years	From 50 to 99 members				
Between 4 and 6 years	More than 600 members				
More than 15 years	From 50 to 99 members				
More than 15 years	From 21 to 49 members				

Regarding your academic	What is the main role you	How many women are the	How many women have k	How long was your patern	Would you like your pater
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3	1	from 1 to 5 days	No, it was enough.
	Project Manager	From 16 to 20	More than 5	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	Less than 3	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Tester	Less than 3	1	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	CTO	Less than 3	1	from 1 to 5 days	No, it was enough.
	Software Engineer	More than 21	More than 5	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Project Manager	From 7 to 10	4	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor	From 7 to 10	1	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Tester	From 7 to 10	4	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	From 4 to 6	1	from 1 to 5 days	No, it was enough.
	Project Manager	From 16 to 20	3	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Usuário gestor.	From 4 to 6	4	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Architect	From 4 to 6	3	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	More than 21	None	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
Up to 20 members	Programmer/Developer	From 4 to 6	2	I did not take paternity leave	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	From 4 to 6	1	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	From 16 to 20	More than 5	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Data Modeling	Less than 3	None	from 21 to 30 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	Less than 3	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor	From 7 to 10	None	I did not take paternity leave	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	From 11 to 15	2	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3	1	from 11 to 20 days	No, it was enough.
	Professor and Researcher	From 11 to 15	4	from 21 to 30 days	No, it was enough.
	Professor and Researcher	From 7 to 10	None	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.

Did you return to the same position and company after becoming father?	If you have changed your	How many employments	Did you maintain the sam
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
No, another role and same company	Após o nascimento de mi	3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		None	Yes
No, another role and another company	When I became a father, I	3	No
Yes, same role and company		None	No
Yes, same role and company	Mudei de carreira por dec	1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		3	No
Yes, same role and company		2	No
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company	Mudei para participar de r	1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	No
Yes, same role and company		2	No
Yes, same role and company		3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		None	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes

Did you work during your	If you worked during your	After you returned to work	Who performs more child	Would you like to participa	If you do not contribute ec
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	em um determinado perio
No			I tend to do more childcar	Yes	Tenho a guarda quase qu
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	Amount of work, more tha
No			The mother does more.	No	Durante o expediente não
No			The mother does more.	Yes	I'm working all day, so I ca
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	I think I contributed equal
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Devido ao tempo que fico
Partially	Deadlines		The mother does more.	Yes	Lack of confidence
Yes			The mother does more.	Yes	Pelo fato de trabalhar dist
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	While in work, I can't cont
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Habilidades específicas
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Face-to-face work with an
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Faltou cultura entre os do
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	We do equally.
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	I would like to spend more
Yes	Prazo de entrega de funcionalidades		I tend to do more childcar	No	Trabalho remoto me prop
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	Procuramos fazer por igua
Yes			The mother does more.	Yes	Contribuo o que posso, ge
Yes			We do share child caregiv	Yes	I contribute equally.
No			I tend to do more childcar	No	Eu costumava participar r
Partially	Problems in a client that only I could quickly resolve		The mother does more.	Yes	She has chosen take care
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	O filho também é meu.
No			We do share child caregiv	No	I contribute equally
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	Dividimos as atividades
Yes	Atividades de orientação remotas.		Eu cuido de um e a ex cu	Yes	Eu moro em Brasília e a e
Yes	Não pude deixar de atender demandas relacionadas		We do share child caregiv	Yes	Acredito que minha contri

After becoming father, ha	Have you ever faced any	In your opinion, do you th	In your opinion, do you th	What challenges and diffic	In your opinion, what chal
Lack of confidence, Overl	não	Definitely	Probably	Por conta do Home office	Além do que ja foi expost
High physical and mental	No	Probably	Possibly	Ajustes de rotina	Ajustes de rotina
Lack of confidence, Overl	Yes, in my last job	Definitely	Definitely	Principalmente concentra	Ter que se precipitar a tuc
Overload (related to child	Não	Probably	Probably	Saber dizer não para algu	Realizar as tarefas do cot
Lack of confidence, Overl	No.	Definitely	Probably	Tiredness from not having	Distrust of everyone, feeli
None	No.	Probably	Probably Not	None	I think, in most cases, wor
Lack of confidence, Overl	Nunca sofri nenhum tipo	Probably	Probably	Trabalhando de casa, que	A falta de rede de apoio p
Sleep deprivation (related	No	Probably Not	Probably Not	Ver que a educação prec	O mesmo da anterior
Overload (related to child	Sim, quando o mesmo fic	Definitely Not	Probably	Principal desafio são os h	Mesmo problema com a f
Overload (related to child	No	Possibly	Possibly	When more work time is r	They naturally are more ir
Sleep deprivation (related	No	Probably	Possibly	Tempo para estar mais pr	Dificuldade para conciliar
Overload (related to child	Loss of sleep and need to	Possibly	Probably	Difficulty in negotiating va	Difficulty in readjusting to
Lack of confidence, Guilty	Não.	Probably	Probably	Falta de disponibilidade p	Falta de compreensão po
Overload (related to child	No	Definitely	Possibly	None	Free time to dedicate to th
Overload (related to child	No.	Probably	Probably Not	it's common for people at	I understand that women
Lack of confidence, Overl	Não	Definitely	Probably Not	Pressão na obrigação de	Dificuldade em receber/as
Sleep deprivation (related	Não	Possibly	Probably Not	Privação de sono	Ficar longe do filho; possí
Overload (related to child	Não	Probably	Probably	Não enfrento pois a empr	Não sei
Overload (related to child	No	Probably Not	Probably Not	Time to spend with the ch	Balancing work and family
Overload (related to child	Não. Apesar dos cuidado	Definitely	Probably	As noites acordado poder	Falta de oportunidades er
Overload (related to child	No.	Possibly	Probably Not	It's very hard to choose b	How to choose between t
Lack of confidence, Overl	Não	Definitely	Definitely	Sobrecarga por não cons	Sobrecarga.
Overload (related to child	Yes mainly related to Slec	Definitely	Probably	Refusal of promotions and	Excessive accumulation c
Sleep deprivation (related	Não prejudicou	Probably Not	Probably Not	Dificuldades com saúde e	Dificuldades com saúde e
Overload (related to child	Não.	Probably	Probably Not	Nenhuma dificuldade.	Para mães de recém-nas
Overload (related to child	Não. Muito pelo contrário.	Definitely	Possibly	O principal desafio é conc	Assédios devido a event

At work, do you believe th	What are your suggestion	Are you willing to implement friendly actions for moms and dads at work?		
Com toda certeza, cultura	Acredito que passa pela h	Definitely		
Não acredito que é muito	No	Probably		
Sim. Infelizmente é comu	Difícil, as realidades sao r	Probably		
Sim, no geral em nossa s	Escola em tempo integral	Probably		
	Extend the period of mate			
	Extend the period of pater			
Yes, mothers suffer much	Decrease the woman's wo	Definitely		
I think it's a reality. Wome	Especialmente para as m	Probably		
Acredito que de forma ge	Políticas institucionais cla	Definitely		
No	As dificuldades são as me	Possibly		
Sim, Pois na maioria das	Uma sugestão é conhece	Possibly		
yes	asdf	Possibly		
Sim. Exige mais afastame	Uma ampliação dos direit	Probably		
I think that for women it is	The period of paternity lea	Definitely		
Com certeza. Desde as o	Criação de leis que garan	Definitely		
Mothers face more difficul	In my case, I work remote	Possibly		
Yes. due to the fact that, f	1) work on demand, 2) wo	Definitely		
Sim pelo fato historico da	Seguridade familiar (segu	Definitely		
As mães sofrem com uma	Mais tempo de licença ma	Definitely		
Enfrentam. Pois algumas	Flexibilização de horário	Definitely		
Mothers are often expecte	Flexible work arrangemer	Probably		
Sim, a gravidez em si e o	Horário flexível e possibili	Definitely		
Yes, because mothers no	Nowadays, I think that to	Possibly		
Sim. Independente da div	Mais compreensão e horá	Definitely		
Yes. Many of the mothers	Reduced working hours, r	Definitely		
Mães tem mais dificultad	O teletrabalho ajuda os p	Probably		
Não vejo essas dificultad	Fazer apenas o possível,	Probably		
Acredito que sim. As mult	Talvez políticas de acom	Definitely		

Carimbo de data/hora	Consent to participate in t	1. Are you a father (biolog	2. In what country do you	In what state do you live?	How old are you?
11/04/2023 12:10:10	Agree	Yes	Brazil	RN	48 to 54 anos
11/04/2023 13:44:16	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	55 to 60 years
11/04/2023 14:07:10	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Federal District	37 to 42 years
11/04/2023 17:18:53	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	43 to 47 years
11/04/2023 17:30:40	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	43 to 47 years
11/04/2023 21:19:10	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	37 to 42 years
11/04/2023 22:58:00	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	37 to 42 years
12/04/2023 07:27:03	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	37 to 42 years
12/04/2023 15:09:33	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Pará	37 to 42 years
12/04/2023 15:20:45	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Maranhão	37 to 42 years
12/04/2023 15:33:45	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Paraná	48 to 54 anos
12/04/2023 17:15:04	Agree	Yes	Brazil	PR	43 to 47 years
12/04/2023 19:34:18	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Pernambuco	43 to 47 years
12/04/2023 20:37:38	Agree	Yes	United States	Arizona	43 to 47 years
12/04/2023 20:41:04	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	55 to 60 years
12/04/2023 21:23:22	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Minas Gerais	31 to 36 years
12/04/2023 21:46:22	Agree	Yes	Brazil	São Paulo	43 to 47 years
12/04/2023 22:21:51	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceará	43 to 47 years
13/04/2023 00:44:57	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Alagoas	37 to 42 years
13/04/2023 06:49:33	Agree	Yes	Germany	Bavaria	31 to 36 years
13/04/2023 16:03:33	Agree	Yes	Iceland	-	31 to 36 years
13/04/2023 16:29:14	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Paraná	37 to 42 years
13/04/2023 17:23:49	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceara	37 to 42 years
13/04/2023 21:39:32	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Tocantins	37 to 42 years
13/04/2023 22:20:31	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Sao Paulo	37 to 42 years
14/04/2023 10:47:47	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	37 to 42 years
14/04/2023 10:52:12	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Alagoas	43 to 47 years
14/04/2023 13:07:55	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	37 to 42 years

What is your marital status	What is the highest level of education	How many children do you have	How old is your youngest child	Do your child (or children) have a disability	What is your family income
Married	PhD	1	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Divorced	Master	1	More than 12 years	No	Up to 7 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	Less than 1 year	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Separated	PhD	1	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	1	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	3	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 9 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Less than 1 year	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	2	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 3 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	4	Less than 1 year	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	3	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Less than 1 year	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Undergraduate Student	2	Less than 1 year	Yes	Up to 7 minimum wages
Married	Master	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	3	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Less than 1 year	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages

Are you currently employed?	What is the nature of your work?	Do you work in the software industry?	How many years of experience do you have?	How many employees do you manage?	How many members are in your organization?
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Private software development	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	State Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	More than 21
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	More than 21
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 11 to 15
Yes, and I work face to face	Private software development	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	Between 4 and 6 years	From 200 to 399 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Research/collaboration project	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	Between 13 and 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Private software development	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Research/collaboration project	Industry	Between 13 and 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 11 to 15
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			

How many years of exper	How many members are	How many years of exper	Regarding your industry	Regarding your industry	Regarding your academic
Between 13 and 15 years	From 21 to 49 members				
		More than 15 years	From 50 to 99 employees	From 11 to 15	More than 15 years
Between 13 and 15 years	From 21 to 49 members				
Between 13 and 15 years	From 50 to 99 members				
More than 15 years	More than 600 members				
Between 10 and 12 years	From 50 to 99 members				
Between 10 and 12 years	From 50 to 99 members				
Between 13 and 15 years	Up to 20 members				
More than 15 years	From 21 to 49 members				
More than 15 years	From 21 to 49 members				
		More than 15 years	From 21 to 49 employees	From 6 to 10	More than 15 years
Between 10 and 12 years	From 50 to 99 members				
		Between 7 and 9 years	More than 600 employees	From 11 to 15	Between 1 and 3 years
Between 7 and 9 years	From 200 to 399 members				
Between 13 and 15 years	Up to 20 members				
		Between 7 and 9 years	From 400 to 599 employe	From 16 to 20	Between 13 and 15 years
Between 10 and 12 years	From 21 to 49 members				
Between 10 and 12 years	Up to 20 members				
		More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	More than 21	More than 15 years
Between 7 and 9 years	From 21 to 49 members				
More than 15 years	From 21 to 49 members				
Between 4 and 6 years	From 21 to 49 members				

Regarding your academic	What is the main role you	How many women are the	How many women have k	How long was your paterr	Would you like your pater
	Professor and Researcher	From 7 to 10		2 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
From 21 to 49 members	Software Engineer	From 4 to 6		1 I did not take paternity leave	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	From 7 to 10	More than 5	from 21 to 30 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor	More than 21	More than 5	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor	More than 21		4 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor	From 16 to 20		2 from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	Less than 3		2 from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Squad Manager	More than 21		5 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor	More than 21		1 from 6 to 10 days	No, it was enough.
	Professor and Researcher	From 4 to 6		1 from 31 to 40 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	From 11 to 15		1 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	From 11 to 15		5 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
More than 600 members	Researcher	From 7 to 10		2 from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor	From 11 to 15	None	from 6 to 10 days	No, it was enough.
	Programmer/Developer	From 4 to 6		2 from 1 to 5 days	No, it was enough.
From 21 to 49 members	Professor	From 4 to 6		2 I did not take paternity leave	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	From 4 to 6	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor	Less than 3		1 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
More than 600 members	Scrum Master	From 7 to 10		1 from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	From 7 to 10		3 more than 120 days	No, it was enough.
	Professor and Researcher	From 4 to 6		4 more than 120 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	Less than 3	None	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	From 4 to 6		2 from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
More than 600 members	Software Engineer/Professor	More than 21	More than 5	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Commercial	From 7 to 10		2 from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	From 4 to 6		3 from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	From 4 to 6	None	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	From 7 to 10	None	from 21 to 30 days	No, it was enough.

Did you return to the same position and company after becoming father?	If you have changed your	How many employments	Did you maintain the sam
Yes, same role and company		3	No
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	No
Yes, same role and company	I am OK where I am.	2	No
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	No
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	No
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	No
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	No
Yes, same role and company		3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		3	Yes

Did you work during your pregnancy?	If you worked during your pregnancy, what was your role?	After you returned to work, how did you manage your workload?	Who performs more child care tasks at home?	Would you like to participate in child care tasks at home?	If you do not contribute equally, what are the reasons?
Partially	Some urgent research work		The mother does more.	Yes	Usually I contribute more
Yes	The needs during my daughter's growth could be met		The mother does more.	Yes	Need to work.
No			The mother does more.	Yes	I'm the only one with formal education
Partially	Projects and deadlines		We do share child care	Yes	Lack of common interest.
No			We do share child care	No	We contribute equally
No			We do share child care	No	-
No			The mother does more.	Yes	The extra workload that I have
No			The mother does more.	Yes	When I become a father, I will have more responsibilities
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Job activities
Partially			The mother does more.	Yes	I am working and my wife is also working
No			I tend to do more child care	No	none
No			We do share child care	Yes	Atividades profissionais
Yes	Money		I tend to do more child care	Yes	-
No			We do share child care	Yes	NA
No			We do share child care	Yes	N/A
No					
No	I was in a project that I played a fundamental role in		The mother does more.	Yes	I got three jobs and she is also working
No			We do share child care	Yes	Contribuímos de forma igual
Partially	Orientação de alunos, escrita de artigos, coordenação de projetos		I tend to do more child care	No	Apesar de ter uma carga de trabalho, não tenho tempo para fazer mais nada
Partially	Precisei corrigir algumas provas que estavam pendentes		We do share child care	Yes	Gostaria de trabalhar mais horas
No			We do share child care	No	-
Partially	Ongoing projects, part-time leave.		We do share child care	Yes	-
No			We do share child care	Yes	Contribuo igualmente.
No			We do share child care	Yes	Dividimos as atividades
No			The mother does more.	Yes	After having acquired more experience, I will be able to do more
Yes	Day to day meetings		The mother does more.	Yes	Hybrid work Model. Work from home
Partially	Mostly quick communication with students		I tend to do more child care	Yes	I have a flexible work schedule
Partially	Respostas de e-mails, projetos de pesquisa, orientação de alunos		We do share child care	Yes	Contribuímos igualmente.
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Work overload

After becoming father, ha	Have you ever faced any	In your opinion, do you th	In your opinion, do you th	What challenges and diffic	In your opinion, what chal
Overload (related to child	No	Definitely	Definitely	How to organize the agen	People may think they are
Overload (related to child	No	Possibly	Possibly	I didn't pay more attention	I think there is still distrust
Overload (related to child	Lack of time	Definitely	Definitely	Lack of time	Lack of time, bad environ
Sleep deprivation (related	No	Possibly	Possibly	Conciliating child care and	Conciliating child care and
Overload (related to child	I had to reduce workload	Probably	Possibly	Colleagues who are not p	Mothers dedicate more ho
Overload (related to child	Diretamente, não. Mas o	Probably	Probably	Nada direto. Somente um -	
Overload (related to child	No	Possibly	Possibly	The main challenge is to b	Balance workload and cor
Overload (related to child	Rarely. Only when my kid	Possibly	Probably Not	Sleep deprivation and get	The same fathers challeng
Overload (related to child	We need to pass more tin	Probably	Probably	No one.	One of the highest is to be
Overload (related to child	No	Probably	Possibly	Mainly sleepy privation ca	Due to breast-feeding the
Overload (related to child	no	Probably	Definitely	Well, sometimes I cannot	less time to work because
Overload (related to child	Sim. A produtividade em	Definitely	Probably	Falta de tempo	Falta de tempo, Falta de c
Overload (related to child	No	Probably Not	Probably Not	Less time to work.	A lot of less time to work.
Lack of confidence, Overl	No.	Probably	Probably	Balance the time at work	Prejudice because of ster
Overload (related to child	No	Definitely Not	Definitely Not	None	None
Overload (related to child	No	Possibly	Probably	Stay with them, have ene	The same, but in general,
Overload (related to child	No	Probably	Probably	Sinto que dividindo de for	Sinto que dividindo de for
High physical and mental	No	Definitely Not	Probably Not	Ter que dividir atenção er	Ter que dividir atenção er
Guilty (related to child act	No	Definitely	Definitely	Nenhum.	Muitos: a sobrecarga de t
Lack of confidence, Overl	No	Probably Not	Probably Not	I cannot be available at al	They need to interrupt the
Lack of confidence, Sleep	No, never.	Possibly	Probably Not	Mainly having to schedule	In Iceland, it tends to be s
Lack of confidence, Sleep	Acredito que, por ser hom	Definitely	Probably	Como homem não encon	Nos espaços públicos, en
Overload (related to child	Queda de performance	Probably	Probably	O meu filho mais velho te	Acredito que o mais difícil
Overload (related to child	No	Definitely	Definitely	I can say that the work, its	I know of a matter of fact,
Sleep deprivation (related	No	Probably	Probably	Financial responsibilities	Double daily shifts
Overload (related to child	No	Probably	Possibly	It is very difficult to sched	The same problems, plus
Overload (related to child	Não.	Definitely	Definitely	Cansaço, restrição de hor	Cansaço, dificuldade de n
Overload (related to child	No	Probably	Probably Not	Reduced availability to wo	In my situation, the same

At work, do you believe th	What are your suggestion	Are you willing to implement friendly actions for moms and dads at work?		
Yes, for sure. The society	Try to improve the activitie	Definitely		
Yes. I think there is still di	Equals oportunities	Probably		
Sim. Algumas demandas,	Licenças maiores. O corre	Probably		
Probably	Cheaper and more acces	Probably		
In general, mothers dedic	Parents (especially single	Definitely		
sim	-	Possibly		
Generally speaking, yes,	It depends greatly on the	Definitely		
I think mothers have a mc	Flexibility of job's times ar	Probably		
Yes. An example of my th	Equality of actions and tas	Definitely		
Yes, due to the previous e	Reduced working hours in	Probably		
Yes, because the society	tempo igual e obrigatório	Definitely		
Sim, acredito que a maior	Como o trabalho geralme	Definitely		
Yes. Unfortunately is a cu	Treat both the same.	Definitely		
Yes. The stereotyping is e	I believe that understandi	Definitely		
No. I believe there is no p	I have no suggestion.	Definitely		
It depends on how things				
In general, men work mor	Equal responsibility and ri	Probably		
Com certeza, historicame	Realizar as divisões de re	Probably		
Sim, pois geralmente elas	Redução de jornada de tr	Probably Not		
Sim, pelo mesmo motivo	1) As pessoas precisam t	Definitely		
Yes. Some people do not	Clear rules	Definitely		
Yes, see above	Depends who is in charge	Definitely		
Dentro do espaço de esco	Creio que a dedicação a r	Definitely		
Sim, pois ainda vivemos e	Eu acho que a curto prazo	Definitely		
I believe that mothers fac	I think that companies are	Definitely		
Yep, especially in areas w	N/A	Definitely		
Yes. First, because the m	Allow remote meetings ar	Probably		
Sim, pelos motivos citado	Legislação, multas, flexibi	Definitely		
Not in my position, I gues	Reduced the workload (in	Definitely		

Carimbo de data/hora	Consent to participate in t	1. Are you a father (biolog	2. In what country do you	In what state do you live?	How old are you?
14/04/2023 15:19:11	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Rio Grande do Sul	37 to 42 years
14/04/2023 19:52:41	Agree	Yes	Brazil	PR	37 to 42 years
14/04/2023 21:08:48	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Paraná	37 to 42 years
15/04/2023 08:42:37	Agree	Yes	Sweden	Stockholm	37 to 42 years
15/04/2023 10:02:47	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	43 to 47 years
15/04/2023 11:00:22	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	43 to 47 years
15/04/2023 15:20:47	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	55 to 60 years
15/04/2023 15:51:52	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	43 to 47 years
15/04/2023 17:27:23	Agree	Yes	Brazil	MT	43 to 47 years
15/04/2023 19:43:40	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	43 to 47 years
15/04/2023 20:07:00	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	37 to 42 years
15/04/2023 20:23:05	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Paraíba	43 to 47 years
15/04/2023 20:40:08	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	55 to 60 years
15/04/2023 20:45:36	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Rio de Janeiro	31 to 36 years
15/04/2023 20:54:51	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Parana	43 to 47 years
15/04/2023 21:30:58	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Goiás	43 to 47 years
15/04/2023 21:40:44	Agree	Yes	Brazil	PR	31 to 36 years
15/04/2023 21:44:20	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Paraná	31 to 36 years
16/04/2023 02:38:51	Agree	Yes	Netherlands	North Holland	37 to 42 years
16/04/2023 08:37:36	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Federal District	31 to 36 years
16/04/2023 10:34:26	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Pernambuco	37 to 42 years
16/04/2023 12:40:57	Agree	Yes	Brazil	RJ	37 to 42 years
16/04/2023 16:08:19	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	43 to 47 years
16/04/2023 19:37:20	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	37 to 42 years

What is your marital status	What is the highest level of education	How many children do you have	How old is your youngest child	Do your child (or children) have a disability	What is your family income
Married	Master	2	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	Up to 9 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	Less than 1 year	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	Master	2	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	More than 12 years	Yes	Up to 9 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	Up to 7 minimum wages
Married	Master	2	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	3	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	Up to 3 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	Master	2	More than 12 years	Yes	Up to 7 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	3	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	1	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	3	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	1	Less than 1 year	Yes	Up to 9 minimum wages
Separated	Master	2	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	Less than 1 year	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Graduated	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 7 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	1	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	3	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages

Are you currently employed?	What is the nature of your organization?	Do you work in the software industry?	How many years of experience do you have in the software industry?	How many employees does your organization have?	How many members are there in your organization?
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Private software development	Industry	Between 10 and 12 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely	Federal Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	State-owned company (Software development)	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 11 to 15
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	More than 21
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	More than 15 years	From 400 to 599 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	Between 13 and 15 years	More than 600 employees	More than 21
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Industry	Between 10 and 12 years	More than 600 employees	From 11 to 15
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Private software development	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	More than 15 years	From 21 to 49 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	More than 21
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	Between 10 and 12 years	More than 600 employees	From 16 to 20

How many years of exper	How many members are	How many years of exper	Regarding your industry	Regarding your industry	Regarding your academic
More than 15 years	From 100 to 199 members				
Between 4 and 6 years	Up to 20 members				
Between 10 and 12 years	From 21 to 49 members				
		More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	More than 21	Less than 1 year
Between 13 and 15 years	Up to 20 members				
		More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	More than 21	Between 13 and 15 years
Between 4 and 6 years	From 50 to 99 members				
Between 13 and 15 years	From 100 to 199 members				
More than 15 years	More than 600 members				
More than 15 years	From 50 to 99 members				
Between 7 and 9 years	From 21 to 49 members				

Regarding your academic	What is the main role you	How many women are the	How many women have k	How long was your paterr	Would you like your pater
	Professor	More than 21		1 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	From 4 to 6		1 from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	Less than 3	None	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	Less than 3	None	more than 120 days	No, it was enough.
Up to 20 members	Programmer/Developer	More than 21	More than 5	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	Less than 3		3 from 21 to 30 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Gerente de Equipe	Less than 3		2 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Project Manager	Less than 3		1 from 6 to 10 days	No, it was enough.
Up to 20 members	Admin	More than 21	More than 5	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Data Modeling	From 4 to 6		1 from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor	More than 21		5 from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor	More than 21	More than 5	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Data Modeling	From 4 to 6		1 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	Less than 3	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	Less than 3	None	I did not take paternity leave	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	From 16 to 20		2 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	From 11 to 15		4 from 21 to 30 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3		1 I did not take paternity leave	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	More than 21		3 from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	More than 21	More than 5	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3		1 from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Project Manager	Less than 3		1 from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	From 7 to 10	None	from 21 to 30 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Líder de desenvolvimento	Less than 3		1 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.

Did you return to the same position and company after becoming father?	If you have changed your	How many employments	Did you maintain the sam
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		2	No
No, another role and same company	I am an associate profess	1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company	Cuidar do desenvolvimen	2	No
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		3	No
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	No
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
No, same role and another company	Salário maior	More than 3	No
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		3	Yes

Did you work during your leave?	If you worked during your leave, what tasks did you perform?	After you returned to work, how did you share child care responsibilities?	Who performs more child care tasks?	Would you like to participate more in child care?	If you do not contribute equally, why not?
No			We do share child care responsibilities.	Yes	
Partially	Some tasks were performed only by me.		We do share child care responsibilities.	Yes	I contributed equally.
Partially	Although I was at paternity leave, it was the end of the semester.		We do share child care responsibilities.	No	I do my best to contribute.
No			I tend to do more child care tasks.	No	I can work more flexibly at home.
Yes			We do share child care responsibilities.	Yes	Time
Yes	I was in a class. It's needed to finish.		We do share child care responsibilities.	Yes	equally
No			The mother does more.	No	Falta de tempo, excesso de tarefas.
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Porque a criança, enquanto eu estava de licença, ficou com a mãe.
No			We do share child care responsibilities.	No	I do.
No			We do share child care responsibilities.	Yes	We contribute equally part-time.
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Possuo dois vinculos empregatícios.
Yes	I was a freelancer at one of the jobs, they had bills to pay.		We do share child care responsibilities.	Yes	NA
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Mais horas de trabalho.
No			We do share child care responsibilities.	Yes	N/A
Yes	Atividade de pesquisa		The mother does more.	Yes	Foco no trabalho
No			We do share child care responsibilities.	No	Eu contribuo de forma igual.
No			We do share child care responsibilities.	No	We already contribute equally.
Yes			I tend to do more child care tasks.	Yes	A mãe dos meus filhos tinha mais tempo.
Partially	Support unanswered team questions		We share as much as possible.	Yes	We share as much as possible.
Yes	Os estudantes não podiam ficar sem aulas e não tinham tempo para estudar.		The mother does more.	Yes	O tempo que fico fora para trabalhar.
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Tento participar de tudo de igual.
Yes	Correção de bugs.		The mother does more.	No	Cuido das tarefas domésticas.
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Por enquanto, minha filha está com a mãe.
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Passo muito tempo fora de casa.

After becoming father, ha	Have you ever faced any	In your opinion, do you th	In your opinion, do you th	What challenges and diffic	In your opinion, what chal
Overload (related to child	No	Possibly	Probably Not	Conciliar o tempo de trabo	Conciliar tempo com os fil
Lack of confidence, Overl	No.	Possibly	Probably Not	After being a father, I coul	Women need to pay more
				Conciliar a família com o t	A começar com o retorno
				Outra dificuldade é alcanç	De modo geral, os ambien
Lack of confidence, Overl	Eu não sofri preconceito,	Probably	Definitely	Uma dificuldade a ser enc	De modo geral, eu diria q
Overload (related to child	No	Probably Not	Definitely Not	Managing time, attending	Same.
Overload (related to child	Lack of time	Definitely	Possibly	Lack of time	Exhaustion
Sleep deprivation (related	i need to take in to and fro	Possibly	Possibly	work times and attention c	the same
Guilty (related to child act	Não	Probably	Probably	Nenhuma	Amamentação, tempo de
Overload (related to child	Não	Probably	Possibly	Conciliar o tempo e atend	Conciliar o tempo e atend
Overload (related to child	No	Possibly	Probably Not	Being a father does not at	Some prejudice of immatu
High physical and mental	No	Possibly	Probably	Quando as crianças estã	Deixar o filho em casa ap
Overload (related to child	Não	Probably	Possibly	As elaborações das aulas	Acredito que o principal d
Lack of confidence, Overl	decrease in production ar	Definitely	Definitely	activities that needed my	greater attention to childre
Sleep deprivation (related	Não	Probably Not	Definitely Not	Dividir a responsabilidade	Jornada dupla, cansa e m
Lack of confidence, Overl	No	Definitely	Definitely	I don't have as much time	They are often have delay
Lack of confidence, Overl	Nao	Probably	Probably	Foco	Foco
Overload (related to child	Sim pois em várias ocasiã	Probably	Definitely	Definitivamente, o machis	Falta de compreensão, di
Lack of confidence, Overl	Never	Probably Not	Possibly	As my daughter is still you	I see that the need to be a
Overload (related to child	Sim, perdi oportunidades	Definitely	Definitely	Dificuldade de cumprir ho	Constante alerta, se o filh
Overload (related to child	No	Definitely	Probably	overlap of parenting and v	Higher load of work becau
Overload (related to child	No	Possibly	Possibly	Tempo limitado para parti	As mesmas que os pais. S
Lack of confidence, High	Não	Possibly	Probably Not	Manter o foco no trabalho	Acho que as maiores dific
Sleep deprivation (related	Ausências pontuais	Definitely	Probably	Menos tempo de ócio.	A divisão de responsabilic
Lack of confidence, Overl	No	Probably Not	Probably Not	When I daughter gets sick	Children, at least until 3 to
Overload (related to child	Não.	Probably	Probably		Creio que por natureza as

At work, do you believe th	What are your suggestion	Are you willing to implement friendly actions for moms and dads at work?		
Eu penso que as mulhere	Diminuição de jornada de	Definitely		
Same answer as above.	Longer leaves and then re	Probably		
	Políticas institucionais de - Assegurar condições de - Com relação ao plano d - Em caso de doenças da Disponibilidade de creche			
No meu trabalho, sim, por		Definitely		
.	.	Definitely		
Yes. Pregnancy is exhaust	Need more time on perso	Definitely		
depends on her family	work time flexibility	Possibly		
Sim. É óbvio.	Trabalho é trabalho, denti	Possibly		
Depende do casal dividir	Oferta de teletrabalho que	Definitely		
Not always.	Everyone should try to en	Definitely		
Sim. A mãe passa mais te	Tele trabalho e flexibilidad	Definitely		
Sim, as mães tem mais di	Trabalhar de forma hibrid	Probably		
for the most part, yes. my	the biggest one: balanced	Definitely		
Sim, muitos não gostam c	Trabalho hibrido ajudaria	Definitely		
Yes. People tend to assur	To be honest, I can't think	Probably		
Sim,vínculo afetivo mais f	Semana de trabalho men	Probably		
Sim, porque as mulheres	Investimento por parte da	Possibly		
I think so. Mothers has na	Facilitating the work from	Definitely		
Sim, geralmente a respon	Flexibilidade de horário, c	Definitely		
Yes. Working on an interr	I mentioned some above.	Definitely		
Sim. A mulher, ao engrav	Propor atividades em hor	Definitely		
Não. A empresa que eu tr	O tempo de licença pater	Possibly		
Com certeza.	Maior liberdade na divisã	Definitely		
Yes.	Paternity and maternity le	Definitely		
Sim.	A empresa em que trabal	Definitely		

Carimbo de data/hora	Consent to participate in t	1. Are you a father (biolog	2. In what country do you	In what state do you live?	How old are you?
16/04/2023 20:04:01	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Federal District	37 to 42 years
16/04/2023 20:25:17	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	37 to 42 years
17/04/2023 01:35:06	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Pernambuco	43 to 47 years
17/04/2023 07:19:24	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito federal	21 to 25 years
17/04/2023 08:52:43	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	43 to 47 years
17/04/2023 09:43:05	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Federal District	31 to 36 years
17/04/2023 10:53:30	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Amazonas	48 to 54 anos
17/04/2023 11:06:44	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Amazonas	48 to 54 anos
17/04/2023 14:27:19	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	31 to 36 years
17/04/2023 15:32:07	Agree	Yes	Brazil	São Paulo	31 to 36 years
17/04/2023 17:54:51	Agree	Yes	Australia	ACT	31 to 36 years
18/04/2023 11:04:57	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	48 to 54 anos
18/04/2023 12:02:42	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	37 to 42 years
18/04/2023 18:59:11	Agree	No			
18/04/2023 21:52:38	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceará	43 to 47 years
18/04/2023 23:26:39	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceara	48 to 54 anos
19/04/2023 08:39:26	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	37 to 42 years
19/04/2023 09:15:01	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceara	37 to 42 years
19/04/2023 10:56:09	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Df	37 to 42 years
19/04/2023 15:20:39	Agree	Yes	Portugal	Algarve	55 to 60 years
19/04/2023 21:18:43	Agree	Yes	Brazil	CE	43 to 47 years
19/04/2023 22:45:39	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceara	43 to 47 years
20/04/2023 10:33:01	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	37 to 42 years
21/04/2023 13:12:35	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Paraná	43 to 47 years
21/04/2023 23:30:48	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	43 to 47 years
22/04/2023 02:31:48	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceará	31 to 36 years
22/04/2023 11:27:05	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	43 to 47 years
22/04/2023 12:18:09	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Goiás	37 to 42 years

What is your marital status	What is the highest level of education	How many children do you have	How old is your youngest child	Do your child (or children) have a disability	What is your family income
Married	Master	2	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Undergraduate Student	1	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	1	More than 12 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	PhD	2	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	3	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Graduated	1	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Divorced	Graduated	1	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	Up to 9 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	Less than 1 year	Yes	Up to 3 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	1	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Graduated	2	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	Master	1	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	Up to 9 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	1	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	Up to 9 minimum wages
Divorced	Especialization	2	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	2	Less than 1 year	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	Graduated	2	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	4	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 9 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	Up to 7 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 10 and 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 7 minimum wages
Married	Master	1	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages

Are you currently employed?	What is the nature of your organization?	Do you work in the software industry?	How many years of experience do you have in the software industry?	How many employees does your organization have?	How many members are there in your organization?
Yes, and I work remotely/	Private software development	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	More than 21
Yes, and I work remotely/	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely/	State-owned company (State-owned)	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	State-owned company (State-owned)	Industry	Between 7 and 9 years	More than 600 employees	More than 21
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely/	Private software development	Industry	Between 13 and 15 years	From 21 to 49 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely/	Private software development	Industry	Between 1 and 3 years	More than 600 employees	From 16 to 20
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Private software development	Industry	More than 15 years	Up to 20 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work remotely/	State-owned company (State-owned)	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely/	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely/	State-owned company (State-owned)	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work face to face	Research/collaboration project	Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely/	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work remotely/	Federal Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely/	State-owned company (State-owned)	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 16 to 20
Yes, and I work in hybrid	State-owned company (State-owned)	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 11 to 15
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	State-owned company (State-owned)	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 16 to 20
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Industry	Less than 1 year	From 100 to 199 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10

How many years of exper	How many members are	How many years of exper	Regarding your industry	Regarding your industry	Regarding your academic
		More than 15 years	From 100 to 199 employe	From 16 to 20	Between 13 and 15 years
		Between 1 and 3 years	More than 600 employees	From 11 to 15	Less than 1 year
Between 10 and 12 years	From 50 to 99 members				
More than 15 years	From 21 to 49 members				
More than 15 years	More than 600 members				
Between 4 and 6 years	From 50 to 99 members				
More than 15 years	Up to 20 members				
		Between 10 and 12 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10	Between 1 and 3 years
		More than 15 years	From 400 to 599 employe	Less than 5	Less than 1 year
Between 10 and 12 years	From 21 to 49 members				
Between 7 and 9 years	From 50 to 99 members				
Between 10 and 12 years	From 100 to 199 members				

Regarding your academic	What is the main role you	How many women are the	How many women have k	How long was your patern	Would you like your pater
	Programmer/Developer	From 4 to 6	2	from 21 to 30 days	No, it was enough.
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3	More than 5	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
From 50 to 99 members	Chief Product & Technol	From 16 to 20	More than 5	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
Up to 20 members	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researche	Less than 3	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	SOC Analyst	From 7 to 10	4	I did not take paternity lea	No, it was enough.
	Professor and Researche	From 11 to 15	More than 5	from 21 to 30 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researche	From 16 to 20	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	Less than 3	None	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Data Scientist	From 4 to 6	1	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Researcher	From 4 to 6	2	more than 120 days	No, it was enough.
	Software Engineer	Less than 3	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	Less than 3	None	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3	None	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	Less than 3	4	from 21 to 30 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researche	Less than 3	1	I did not take paternity lea	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3	1	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
More than 600 members	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3	More than 5	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
Up to 20 members	Professor and Researche	Less than 3	More than 5	from 51 to 60 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3	More than 5	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	Less than 3	None	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researche	From 7 to 10	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	IT Manegement	Less than 3	None	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Project Manager	Less than 3	1	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researche	From 16 to 20	More than 5	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor	Less than 3	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	From 7 to 10	3	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.

Did you return to the same position and company after becoming father?	If you have changed your	How many employments	Did you maintain the sam
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		2	No
No, another role and another company		1	No
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		None	Yes
Yes, same role and company		None	Yes
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	No
Yes, same role and company	Haven't been back yet.	None	Yes
Yes, same role and company		3	No
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		None	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company	Eu saí da área operacional	1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
No, another role and same company	Não houve mudanças. Ap	2	No
Yes, same role and company	I did become Data Scienc	1	Yes

Did you work during your	If you worked during your	After you returned to work	Who performs more child	Would you like to participa	If you do not contribute ec
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Heavy workload
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	-
Yes	Minha esposa estava com contrato de trabalho sus		We try to do share child c	Yes	Naturalmente a criança n
Partially			We do share child caregiv	Yes	Tempo
Partially	The deadlines were set before the paternity leave ar		We do share child caregiv	Yes	They are equal
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	I contributed equally
Partially	complete some commitments		The mother does more.	Yes	lack of planning and time
No			The mother does more.	Yes	work
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	-
No			We do share child caregiv	No	i do contribute equally
No			We do share child caregiv	No	We try to contribute equal
Yes	I was software house coordinator / engineering and		The mother does more.	Yes	work activities and studyin
No			I tend to do more childcar	Yes	The mother work hours is
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Falta de tempo por conta
No			The mother does more.	No	Different task, different pe
Yes	Company demand		We do share child caregiv	Yes	I contribute
No			I tend to do more childcar	Yes	menos dedicação da parc
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	Na
No			The mother does more.	Yes	habits of Portuguese motf
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	-
No			We do share child caregiv	No	.
Partially			I tend to do more childcar	Yes	Fico mais com as criança
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Minha esposa contribui m
Yes	Não trabalhei.		The mother does more.	Yes	Infelizmente eu não estou
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	Tento cuidar do meu filho
Partially	Resolver o problema do acúmulo de atividade que c		The mother does more.	Yes	Existem atividades que sc
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	I do.

After becoming father, ha	Have you ever faced any	In your opinion, do you th	In your opinion, do you th	What challenges and diffic	In your opinion, what chal
Overload (related to child	No	Definitely Not	Definitely Not	More responsibility	Time managing between t
Sleep deprivation (related	No	Probably Not	Definitely Not	None	Lack of time
Lack of confidence, Overl	Não	Possibly	Possibly	Eaustãoofísica e mental	Muito mais exaustão física
Sleep deprivation (related	Não	Probably Not	Probably Not	Tempo	Tempo
Lack of confidence, Overl	No	Definitely	Definitely	To share my time between	Overload of domestic wor
Lack of confidence, Overl	None	Probably Not	Probably Not	Sometimes I need to leav	Mother"s generally have r
Overload (related to child	it is difficult to answer, but	Definitely	Possibly	adjust my time to dedicate	difficulties reconciling mot
High physical and mental	No	Definitely	Probably	Today, my children are all	fatigue, double shift
Lack of confidence, Overl	no	Probably	Probably	Manage a sick boy at hon	Manage a sick boy at hon
Overload (related to child	during the child sick days	Probably Not	Probably Not	sometimes i need to leave	same as myself as a fathe
Overload (related to child	No, I haven't.	Probably	Possibly	The main issue in the first	I believe they are similar t
High physical and mental	not from company but per	Definitely		none	people tend to diminishir
Happiness	No	Possibly	Possibly	Timeshare between the cl	Timeshare between the cl
Overload (related to child	Não	Possibly	Definitely Not	A principal dificuldade é e	Conciliar trabalho com fér
Guilty (related to child act	I'd like to work more than	Probably	Probably	I'd like to pay more attent	They have to, or are comp
Lack of confidence, Overl	No	Definitely	Definitely	O meu maior desafio, sen	Precisam estar disponível
Overload (related to child	menos produtividade	Probably	Probably	proporcionar atenção qua	equalizar preocupações, r
Overload (related to child	No	Probably Not	Possibly	Balance work with family	Balance work with family
Overload (related to child	not that I realized	Definitely	Probably	the need to leave on time	mothers may face a varie
Overload (related to child	-	Probably Not	Definitely Not	Often I have to assist my	Same
Lack of confidence, Overl	Sim, alguns se mostram s	Probably	Possibly	Conciliar o trabalho com a	Conciliar o trabalho com a
Lack of confidence, Overl	Não	Probably	Possibly	Carga horária	A paternidade/maternidad
Lack of confidence, Sleep	No	Definitely	Possibly	Pelo trabalho não vejo ne	Além do preconceito exist
Guilty (related to child act	Não.	Possibly	Possibly	Hoje eu não enfrento nen	Na minha opinião as mãe
Overload (related to child	Não	Definitely	Definitely	Algumas tarefas não cons	Ter que se ausentar para
Sleep deprivation (related	Não	Possibly	Possibly	Dificuldade em conciliar o	Dificuldade em conciliar o
Overload (related to child	No.	Probably	Definitely Not	I have little license (in hou	Mothers many times don't

At work, do you believe th	What are your suggestion	Are you willing to implement friendly actions for moms and dads at work?		
No, for me the womans ha	I think the best solution is	Definitely		
No	Flexible time	Possibly		
Com certeza	Difícil, acredito que compo	Probably		
Não	Organizar e planejar melh	Possibly		
Definitely! Mothers usually	To change corporate mind	Probably		
I think there are more solc	Home office, planing, ben	Definitely		
?	To share child care respo	Definitely		
Yes, basically because of	psychological follow-up	Probably		
-	-	Definitely Not		
it depends to each case. I	Communication and Conc	Possibly		
	The example we have at t			
Not really - see the answe	I'm not 100% sure but I be			
	There's also the inherent	Probably		
yes. more bias against a v	in brazil full time schools v	Definitely		
I dont know	Reduce parents' work hou	Definitely		
Acredito que sim, pois as	Manter um ritmo de trabal	Definitely		
I'm living in a country that	That's a cultural challenge	Probably		
Sim! As mulheres de mod	Eu acredito que uma emp	Definitely		
sim. em grande maioria, r	horário flexível, metas rea	Probably		
Yes. Our society puts mo	Same paternity leave wou	Definitely		
mothers can experiencin	There are several ways in	Definitely		
No	-	Possibly		
Sim.	Mudanças na legislação.	Definitely		
Não necessariamente. A	Espaços infantis no trabal	Definitely		
Sim. Elas acabam enfren	É necessária uma mudan	Definitely		
Sim. Para mim as mulher	Organizar melhor sua roti	Definitely		
Sim. Dependendo da emp	Ter empatia, pois as situa	Definitely		
Embora a responsabilidac	Restringir o uso da tecnol	Possibly		
Sometimes Yes.	More flexibility of schedul	Definitely		

Carimbo de data/hora	Consent to participate in t	1. Are you a father (biolog	2. In what country do you	In what state do you live?	How old are you?
22/04/2023 14:42:36	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito federal	37 to 42 years
22/04/2023 19:10:07	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Tocantins	31 to 36 years
23/04/2023 18:30:19	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	more than 61 years
23/04/2023 21:34:26	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Brasilia	31 to 36 years
24/04/2023 10:27:01	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Fedral	more than 61 years
24/04/2023 10:58:51	Agree	Yes	Brazil	BA	37 to 42 years
24/04/2023 11:09:02	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	43 to 47 years
24/04/2023 11:58:19	Agree	Yes	Brazil	bahia	55 to 60 years
24/04/2023 12:14:58	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Brasilia	48 to 54 anos
24/04/2023 12:41:06	Agree	Yes	Brazil	District Federal	48 to 54 anos
24/04/2023 12:47:38	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	48 to 54 anos
24/04/2023 13:44:04	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Brasília	31 to 36 years
24/04/2023 14:17:32	Agree	Yes	Brazil	São Paulo	37 to 42 years
24/04/2023 14:33:37	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	37 to 42 years
24/04/2023 14:43:19	Agree	Yes	Spain	Valencia	43 to 47 years
24/04/2023 14:54:31	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Bahia	37 to 42 years
24/04/2023 15:27:54	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	31 to 36 years
24/04/2023 16:18:02	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	31 to 36 years
24/04/2023 16:47:01	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	55 to 60 years
24/04/2023 18:13:53	Agree	No			
25/04/2023 09:14:37	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Ceará	31 to 36 years
25/04/2023 10:35:49	Agree	No			
25/04/2023 13:21:05	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Distrito Federal	48 to 54 anos
25/04/2023 14:19:13	Agree	Yes	Brazil	Pernambuco	31 to 36 years
25/04/2023 15:50:39	Agree	Yes	Brazil	DF	37 to 42 years
25/04/2023 19:48:20	Agree	Yes	Brazil	MS	37 to 42 years
25/04/2023 22:35:43	Agree	Yes	United States	California	31 to 36 years

What is your marital status	What is the highest level of education	How many children do you have	How old is your youngest child	Do your child (or children) have a disability	What is your family income
Married	PhD	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	2	Less than 1 year	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Divorced	Master	2	More than 12 years	Yes	Up to 3 minimum wages
Long-term relationship	Graduated	1	More than 12 years	No	Up to 7 minimum wages
Divorced	Master	5	More than 12 years	No	More than 10 minimum wages
Single	Master	1	Between 10 and 12 years	No	Up to 7 minimum wages
Separated	Especialization	3	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	3	More than 12 years	No	Up to 3 minimum wages
Married	Master	2	More than 12 years	Yes	Up to 9 minimum wages
Married	Graduated	2	More than 12 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Long-term relationship	Graduated	1	More than 12 years	No	Up to 7 minimum wages
Divorced	Especialization	1	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	Up to 7 minimum wages
Divorced	Master	2	More than 12 years	No	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Graduated	1	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	Up to 5 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 4 and 6 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Prefer not to answer	Especialization	1	More than 12 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	3	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Master	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Long-term relationship	Master	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Especialization	2	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	Up to 7 minimum wages
Long-term relationship	Master	1	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	Graduated	3	Between 1 and 3 years	Yes	More than 10 minimum wages
Married	PhD	1	Between 7 and 9 years	Yes	Up to 7 minimum wages

Are you currently employed?	What is the nature of your organization?	Do you work in the software industry?	How many years of experience do you have in the software industry?	How many employees does your organization have?	How many members are there in your organization?
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Industry	Between 1 and 3 years	More than 600 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work face to face	Private software development	Academia			
No	Private software development	Academia			
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	From 50 to 99 employees	From 11 to 15
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Academia			
No	Private software development	Industry	Between 1 and 3 years	From 200 to 399 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 11 to 15
Yes, and I work face to face	State Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	From 50 to 99 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	Between 7 and 9 years	From 21 to 49 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	More than 15 years	From 21 to 49 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work face to face	Federal Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Private software development	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 16 to 20
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	More than 21
Yes, and I work remotely	Federal Public Administration	Industry	Between 13 and 15 years	More than 600 employees	From 11 to 15
Yes, and I work in hybrid	Federal Public Administration	Industry and Academia			
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	Between 10 and 12 years	More than 600 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work face to face	State-owned company (SOE)	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	Between 10 and 12 years	More than 600 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely	Federal Public Administration	Industry	More than 15 years	More than 600 employees	Less than 5
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	More than 15 years	Up to 20 employees	From 6 to 10
Yes, and I work remotely	Private software development	Industry	Between 4 and 6 years	From 200 to 399 employees	From 11 to 15

Regarding your academic	What is the main role you	How many women are the	How many women have k	How long was your paterr	Would you like your pater
From 50 to 99 members	Professor	From 11 to 15	More than 5	from 21 to 30 days	No, it was enough.
	Researcher	Less than 3		1 from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor and Researcher	Less than 3	None	I did not take paternity leave	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Researcher	Less than 3	None	from 1 to 5 days	No, it was enough.
	Project Manager	From 4 to 6		2 I did not take paternity leave	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Professor	Less than 3	More than 5	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Requirements Analyst	Less than 3		1 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
More than 600 members	Professor	More than 21		2 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
Up to 20 members	Researcher	From 4 to 6		2 from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	BI Consultant	From 4 to 6		2 I did not take paternity leave	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Análise de redes	Less than 3		1 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Requirements Analyst	Less than 3	More than 5	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3		1 I did not take paternity leave	Yes, I'd like more days.
From 50 to 99 members	Software Tester	Less than 3	None	from 21 to 30 days	No, it was enough.
	Sr Manager	From 7 to 10	More than 5	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
Up to 20 members	Software Engineer	Less than 3		1 from 61 to 120 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Auditor	From 4 to 6		1 from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Software Engineer	Less than 3	None	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
From 50 to 99 members	Project Manager	From 11 to 15	More than 5	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Data Scientist	Less than 3	More than 5	from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3		1 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Programmer/Developer	Less than 3	None	from 6 to 10 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Project Manager	Less than 3	None	from 11 to 20 days	Yes, I'd like more days.
	Project Manager	Less than 3	None	from 6 to 10 days	No, it was enough.
	Director of R&D	Less than 3		1 from 1 to 5 days	Yes, I'd like more days.

Did you return to the same position and company after becoming father?	If you have changed your	How many employments	Did you maintain the sam
Yes, same role and company		3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company	Higher wage	None	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	No
Yes, same role and company	Yes. A lot of expenses an	2	No
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	No
Yes, same role and company	a unica salario e por caus	More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company	no change	3	Yes
Yes, same role and company	Salary, quality of life and r	2	Yes
No, another role and same company	Após a paternidade fui de	More than 3	No
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes
Yes, same role and company		1	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company	I have changed. Looking f	More than 3	Yes
No, another role and same company	Sai de uma empresa priva	2	No
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
No, another role and another company	Mudei para o setor públic	More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	No
Yes, same role and company		3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		3	Yes
Yes, same role and company	Exaustão no trabalho ante	1	Yes
No, another role and another company	Tive que deixar a Coorde	More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		More than 3	Yes
Yes, same role and company		2	Yes

Did you work during your	If you worked during your	After you returned to work	Who performs more child	Would you like to participa	If you do not contribute ec
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Eu acabo tendo mais ativi
No			I tend to do more childcar	Yes	Acredito que as tarefas de
Yes	There was no law for paternity leave		The mother does more.	Yes	Less time at home
No			The mother does more.	No	Oportunidade
Yes	At the time there was no paternity leave and it made		The mother does more.	Yes	ack of time. Reason for ha
Yes			The mother does more.	Yes	I live in other city that my c
No			The mother does more.	Yes	Time management, lack c
No	nao		We do share child caregiv	Yes	nao
No	have not worked		The mother does more.	No	certain activities, such as
Yes	Paternity leave is exclusive to women.		We do share child caregiv	No	Lack of time
No	Durante a paternidade exerci trabalho formal fora de		We do share child caregiv	Yes	Durante 12 anos fui o prin
Yes			I tend to do more childcar	Yes	Eu contribuo equalitariam
Yes	A falta de preparação financeira adequada para a si		The mother does more.	Yes	Priorizar o custeio da fam
Partially	Falta de substituto, tarefas de grande complexidade		The mother does more.	Yes	Meu cargo de chefia me t
Yes	Transformation project and lack os skills to replace r		We do share child caregiv	Yes	not aplicable
Yes			We do share child caregiv	Yes	Fazemos de forma equilib
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	Time in work
Yes	Em 2009 quando minha filha nasceu legalmente só		We do share child caregiv	Yes	Quando minha filha era re
Partially			We do share child caregiv	Yes	No, reason
No			The mother does more.	Yes	During the first six months
No			We do share child caregiv	No	Nós dividimos os cuidado
Partially	Dependência da empresa com a minha pessoa		The mother does more.	Yes	Trabalho
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	Existem algumas atividad
No			We do share child caregiv	No	Penso que contribuimos i
No			We do share child caregiv	Yes	I have less time to dedica

After becoming father, ha	Have you ever faced any	In your opinion, do you th	In your opinion, do you th	What challenges and diffic	In your opinion, what chal
Overload (related to child	No	Probably	Probably Not	Privação de sono	Privação de sono. Respo
Overload (related to child	Não	Probably	Probably Not	Viagens longas.	Tempo para amamentaçã
High physical and mental	No	Definitely	Definitely	Pressure for being absent	concern about loosing the
Sleep deprivation (related	Nao	Definitely	Possibly	O fato de nao poder ficar	Assédio
High physical and mental	No. have always been ve	Probably	Probably Not	lack of time for activities o	I think in sharing chores a
Sleep deprivation (related	No	Possibly	Possibly	Nothing	Double journey and respo
High physical and mental	Not really.	Definitely	Possibly	Major difficulty is to balan	Lack of time to offer breas
Lack of confidence, Overl	nao	Possibly	Possibly	assedio moral por causa	falta de creches e turnos ;
Overload (related to child	No, have never faced that	Possibly	Possibly	worries and time competit	availability of time and de
Overload (related to child	No. Everyone knows it's a	Possibly	Definitely Not	Answering my wife's call a	Body and mind in differen
Overload (related to child	Não. Os prejuízos se der	Definitely	Possibly	Provimento financeiro, de	Desafio educacional, ater
Lack of confidence, Overl	No	Probably	Probably	Cuidados com a saúde, fe	Preconceito, senso de inc
High physical and mental	Sim.	Definitely	Definitely	Quando o homem particip	A sociedade é estruturalm
Overload (related to child	Já aconteceu duas vezes	Probably	Probably Not	Muita saudade!	Entendo que a necessida
Overload (related to child	Yes, lack of travel and lac	Probably	Definitely	Too many tasks at same t	Too many tasks at same t
Lack of confidence, Overl	Sim, ao avisar que não p	Probably	Probably	Levar na escola e chegar	Horários não flexíveis, dis
High physical and mental	No	Possibly	Possibly	The noise and the attentio	Fixed journeys
Overload (related to child	No	Probably	Probably Not	Horário da jornada de trat	As maiores dificuldades s
Lack of confidence, Overl	Yes, segregation	Probably	Definitely	Do well both jobs, father	Time Sharing
Overload (related to child	Never	Definitely	Probably	Home office provides the	Traditionally mothers have
Overload (related to child	Não	Definitely Not	Definitely Not	Nenhum	Nenhum
Overload (related to child	Não	Probably Not	Definitely Not	Não poder dar muita aten	Ficar longe dos filhos
Lack of confidence, Overl	Sim. Como tive que ir ao	Definitely	Probably	O trabalho não está prep	Dificuldade em dedicar m
Sleep deprivation (related	não	Possibly	Probably Not	Jornada dupla ou tripla, c	Jornada dupla ou tripla, c
Overload (related to child	No	Definitely	Definitely	No specific challenges as	On top of the general cha

At work, do you believe th	What are your suggestion	Are you willing to implement friendly actions for moms and dads at work?		
Com certeza	Só o tempo resolverá a pi	Probably Not		
Acredito que sim. Mães n	Flexibilidade de horário.	Definitely		
Yes.	Regulation and more sever	Definitely		
Nao, pois cada um tem su	Mais respeito e consciênc	Definitely		
Yes. I believe that mother	Greater flexibility in the tir	Probably		
I think yes.	Planning	Possibly		
Cultural tradition may imo	breast-feeding support (tir	Definitely		
sim, por que o pai sempr	turno de 6 horas no trabal	Possibly		
culturally, the demands ar	probably any law support	Possibly		
Yes. The maternal need t	It would be great if the wo	Definitely		
Sim. Mães necessitam de	Trabalho remoto de ambc	Probably		
Provavelmente sim, caso	Dividir atividades e mudai	Definitely		
Sim.	Não tenho sugestões.	Definitely		
Entendo que os problema	Acho que as licenças pod	Definitely		
If I look to me, no. If I look	Work from home, less hou	Possibly		
Não, acredito que a socie	Respeito e os que não qu	Definitely		
Yes, due to breastfeeding	Flexible journey	Probably		
Sim, porque geralmente a	Trabalho remoto para pai	Definitely		
Yes, the Work is harder fo	Help each other. Parents	Definitely		
For sure.	Shared paternity/maternit	Definitely		
Creio que não	Colaboração dos pais	Definitely		
Acho que a mãe sente ma	Não sei informar	Possibly		
Sim. Inegavelmente na sc	Deve existir mais conscie	Probably		
sim, principalmente nos p	amadurecimento das emp	Definitely Not		
I'm sure they do. This is c	More flexibility in difficult t	Definitely		